

Internal Audit Quality and Public Sector Performance in Nigeria

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Abstract

Despite the critical role of internal auditing in enhancing public sector performance, its specific impact on key performance indicators such as compliance, revenue target achievement, revenue collection, and performance accountability within the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) remains underexplored. This study aims to examine the influence of internal audit quality on public sector performance accountability within FIRS in Oyo State, Nigeria. A descriptive research design was employed, and data was collected from a sample of 320 respondents drawn from a total population of 9,800 FIRS staff using random sampling techniques. The Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size, and data was gathered through structured questionnaires. Findings indicate that internal audit competence positively impacts compliance at FIRS ($X=2.83$; $SD=0.49$). Internal audit control contributes significantly to meeting revenue targets ($X=2.93$; $SD=0.52$). Internal audit monitoring enhances revenue collection ($X=3.05$; $SD=0.52$). Also, there is a strong relationship between internal audit quality and public sector accountability ($X=3.67$; $SD=0.54$). Hypotheses testing revealed a significant combined influence of internal audit competence, control, monitoring, and quality on public sector accountability in FIRS ($F=14.575$, $p < 0.05$). Further, the relative influence of these variables was significant: internal audit competence ($\beta = 0.147$, $t = 2.357$, $p = 0.019$), internal audit control ($\beta = 0.202$, $t = 1.064$, $p = 0.008$), internal audit monitoring ($\beta = 0.302$, $t = 3.120$, $p = 0.000$), and internal audit quality ($\beta = 0.198$, $t = 1.786$, $p = 0.000$). The study recommends that FIRS align internal audit functions with strategic goals, invest in continuous professional training, and enhance audit independence to improve compliance and revenue generation. Strengthening audit monitoring and establishing a robust system for implementing audit recommendations will further improve accountability and governance.

Key Words: Accountability, Compliance, Internal audit, Public sector, Revenue collection

1.0 Introduction

Public sector accountability plays a critical role in ensuring the effective governance of public resources and maintaining the trust of citizens. It involves the obligation of government entities, public officials, and civil servants to justify their actions and decisions to the public and relevant stakeholders, thus fostering transparency, responsibility, and ethical behavior (Aleksavska, 2021; Oyedokun, & Felejaye, 2022). Key elements of public sector accountability include transparency, which provides citizens with access to government operations; responsibility, which mandates adherence to established rules; answerability, where officials must defend their decisions; and control mechanisms to ensure oversight and ethical standards that align actions with the public interest (Arun et al., 2021). These principles collectively ensure that public administration serves society's best interests, fostering fairness and compliance with the rule of law. In Nigeria, public sector accountability remains a significant concern, with institutions facing challenges in curbing corruption, financial mismanagement, and inefficiency. Despite frameworks like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), accountability remains hindered by endemic corruption and weak institutional capacity (Ndukwe et al., 2021). Public sector fraud, including ghost workers, embezzlement, and financial irregularities, depletes billions of Naira annually from national resources, impeding socio-economic development and governance efforts (Wokocha et al., 2018). Historical weaknesses in control mechanisms, particularly since the oil boom years, have exacerbated corrupt practices, reflecting a broader absence of accountability and ethical governance (Okere et al., 2018; Oyedokun, & Oyetunji, 2022).

Internal auditing has emerged as a critical tool for enhancing accountability in the public sector by providing oversight, monitoring financial practices, and ensuring compliance with policies. Defined as an independent and systematic evaluation of an organization's operations, internal auditing helps to mitigate risks, detect fraud, and ensure the efficient use of public resources (Bello et al., 2018; Abdulazeez, Adetola, & Oyedokun, 2023). Through its systematic and disciplined approach, internal auditing strengthens the effectiveness of risk management, governance processes, and compliance with regulations (Tapang & Ibiam, 2019). The internal auditor serves as the "watchdog" within organizations, ensuring the appropriate allocation of financial resources, monitoring compliance, and preventing theft or misappropriation of funds (Abdulrahman, 2020; Oyedokun & Muhammad, 2023). The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), tasked with tax assessment, collection, and accounting in Nigeria, exemplifies the importance of internal auditing for accountability. With its mandate including taxes such as the Petroleum Profit Tax, Companies Income Tax, and Value-Added Tax, the FIRS plays a critical role in ensuring compliance with revenue targets and financial regulations (Kamaliah et al., 2018; Oyedokun, & Muhammad, 2023). Effective internal audits within FIRS are essential for identifying fraud, poor management, and irregularities, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of public sector accountability and the maximization of public resources (Kupec, 2017; Oyedokun, & Olayinka, 2024).

1.1 Statement of Problem

Despite the critical role of internal auditing in enhancing public sector performance, its specific impact on key performance indicators compliance, revenue target achievement, revenue collection, and performance accountability within the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) remains underexplored. Existing literature predominantly focuses on general internal auditing practices or private sector applications, neglecting the unique challenges and effectiveness of internal auditing in tax administration. This knowledge gap hinders a comprehensive understanding of how internal audit quality influences performance in the FIRS, limiting the potential for informed improvements in public sector accountability and effectiveness in achieving organizational goals. This study seeks to address this gap.

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine the influence of Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- i. assess the effect of internal Audit competence on compliance in Federal Inland Revenue Service;
- ii. analyse the effect of Internal Audit control on meeting the revenue targets in Federal Inland Revenue Service;
- iii. establish the impact of internal audit monitoring on revenue collection in Federal Inland Revenue Service; and
- iv. determine the effect of internal audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service.

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the stated objectives, the following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What is the effect of Internal Audit competence on compliance in Federal Inland Revenue Service?
2. What is the effect of Internal Audit control on meeting the revenue targets in Federal Inland Revenue Service?
3. Does Internal Audit monitoring have an impact on revenue collection in Federal Inland Revenue Service?
4. What is the effect of Internal Audit functions on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

1.4 Hypotheses

The hypothesis stated below will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: To what extent does the combined influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

Ho2: To what extent does Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality influence public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Principles of Accountability of Public Sector's Funds

Accountability and transparency are essential components of good governance, particularly in managing public sector funds. Transparency ensures timely, accurate, and relevant financial reporting, while accountability provides a framework for responsible financial management and adherence to legal and regulatory obligations. Together, these principles strengthen trust in public institutions, improve resource allocation, and combat corruption (Hutapea & Hapsari, 2021; Oyedokun, & Adewuyi, 2022). To achieve accountability, public sector entities must adhere to audit mandates, publish timely reports, and maintain clear communication of objectives and strategies with stakeholders (Umar-Dauda, & Oyedokun, 2018; Marwiyah et al., 2023). Auditors play a critical role by implementing international standards, conducting risk-based assessments, and ensuring transparency in financial and operational processes (Natisation, et al., 2022). High ethical standards, including integrity and avoidance of conflicts of interest, are integral to accountability. Public reporting of audit findings, even in challenging circumstances such as during the COVID-19 pandemic, ensures that public funds are used responsibly (Sari & Muslim, 2023). Moreover, public sector entities must foster transparency by making audit findings accessible and comprehensible to all stakeholders, promoting informed decision-making and active public participation (Oyedokun, Naburgi, & AKWE, Kennedy, 2020; Suhardi et al., 2023).

2.2 Measures of Accountability in FIRS

1. Compliance with Rules of Engagement

Compliance with rules of engagement is critical for the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) to maintain accountability within its operations. The internal audit function ensures adherence to organizational policies, promoting ethical and professional practices that align with the FIRS vision and mission. Internal auditors are tasked with validating financial transactions and enforcing

regulatory compliance to support FIRS' objectives, such as delivering quality taxpayer services and fostering voluntary compliance (Bilouseac & Zaharia, 2023).

The internal audit function validates financial execution, ensuring compliance with established standards and rules. Key services include assessing individuals and enterprises chargeable with tax, enforcing payment collection, and promoting compliance with relevant laws. By enforcing compliance with tax regimes and investigating tax fraud, the internal audit team strengthens accountability and prevents misuse of public funds (Akinleye & Ogunmakin, 2023).

2. Revenue Remittance

The FIRS is responsible for assessing, collecting, and remitting taxes efficiently. Internal auditors play a pivotal role in monitoring that revenues are appropriately channeled to government accounts in a timely manner. This oversight prevents corruption, builds trust, and enhances the efficiency of public resource management (Appiah et al., 2023). Internal audits ensure adherence to the remittance policies by tracking collection activities, verifying transactions, and ensuring that no funds are lost to inefficiencies or fraudulent practices. This process aligns with the broader goal of increasing financial accountability and ensuring effective public fund management (Sari & Muslim, 2023).

3. Revenue Target

FIRS establishes revenue targets annually to enhance tax collection. Internal audit mechanisms ensure these targets are met by consistently monitoring departmental progress and sending reminders. For instance, the FIRS set a revenue target of N12 trillion in 2023, emphasizing the integration of technology to widen the tax net. Internal audits monitor these efforts to ensure alignment with performance benchmarks (**Public Sector Magazine, 2024**). By assessing the adherence to set targets, internal audits not only track revenue performance but also highlight areas needing intervention, ensuring the efficiency and transparency of revenue generation strategies (Msindwana & Ngwakwe, 2022).

2.3 Internal Auditing

The concept of auditing has its roots in the 15th century when it was primarily conducted to prevent fraud in financial records maintained by stewards of wealthy estates. Over time, the role of auditing evolved from basic verification to a more systematic process of validating financial statements. Today, auditing is integral to corporate governance, ensuring transparency and accountability within organizations (Bilouseac & Zaharia, 2023). In modern times, internal auditing has shifted from its traditional role of verifying bills and detecting fraud to a more comprehensive evaluation of operational efficiency, effectiveness, and adherence to organizational policies (Appiah et al.,

2023). This development is attributed to increasing organizational complexity and the need for robust risk management practices.

2.3.1 Internal Audit Quality

Internal audit quality refers to the effectiveness and reliability of internal auditing processes in providing accurate assessments and recommendations. A high-quality internal audit evaluates operational efficiency, ensures compliance with regulations, and provides a framework for better decision-making (Oyedokun, Kujore, Dopemu, & Famuyiwa, 2023; Alqudah, 2024)

Internal auditors are responsible for analyzing and improving internal control systems, which include financial operations, risk management, and governance structures. Their role involves identifying inefficiencies and proposing actionable recommendations to optimize organizational performance (Msindwana & Ngwakwe, 2022).

2.3.2 Internal Audit Independence

The independence of internal auditing is a cornerstone for its effectiveness. Independence ensures that auditors operate without undue influence, allowing them to make unbiased assessments and report findings objectively. Internal auditors must maintain a high degree of professional integrity, adhere to ethical standards, and provide impartial evaluations (Njagi, 2023). Internal auditing departments typically report to an organization's highest level of governance, such as the board of directors or audit committees, to enhance their autonomy and credibility. This independence fosters stakeholder trust and enhances the organization's governance framework (Aidi et al., 2022).

2.3.3 Internal Audit Competencies

1. Competence: Competence refers to the professional qualifications, technical expertise, and ethical conduct of internal auditors. Competent auditors possess advanced skills in governance, risk assessment, and control evaluation, enabling them to provide valuable insights to management (Aidi et al., 2022). Studies highlight that organizations with competent audit staff are more likely to achieve higher levels of operational efficiency and accountability. Training and continuous professional development are essential for maintaining high levels of competence within audit functions (Mpakaniye, 2022).

2. Risk Assessment: Internal auditors play a vital role in identifying and mitigating organizational risks. Their risk assessment activities involve evaluating financial systems, compliance practices, and operational vulnerabilities (Mate, 2022). Competence in risk assessment enables internal auditors to develop tailored strategies that address specific organizational challenges, thereby strengthening the organization's risk management framework. Effective risk assessments also contribute to fraud prevention and improved financial reporting quality (Pratiwi et al., 2024).

3. Fraud Detection: Fraud detection is a critical component of internal auditing. Competent auditors use advanced techniques, including data analytics and forensic accounting, to identify fraudulent activities. Organizations with robust internal audit functions are better equipped to detect and mitigate fraud risks (Odeyemi et al., 2024). Fraud detection requires auditors to have deep knowledge of organizational processes and financial systems, enabling them to recognize irregularities and recommend corrective actions (Kabuye et al., 2017).

4. Evaluation of Controls: Internal auditors assess the effectiveness of internal control systems to ensure that organizational objectives are achieved. Effective control evaluation reduces the likelihood of fraud, improves operational efficiency, and enhances the accuracy of financial reporting (Mukhina, 2015).

Internal auditors must also ensure that controls are adaptable to changing business environments. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of controls are essential for maintaining compliance with regulations and achieving strategic goals.

2.4 Empirical Review

Mohammed and Buba (2023) examined the effect of financial regulations on accountability in Nigerian public organizations. Their study revealed that strict compliance with internal audit reviews significantly enhances transparency and accountability in financial transactions. Hammayo et al. (2022) investigated the determinants of internal audit effectiveness in Nigeria's federal public sector and found that audit quality, competence, and management support are key factors driving effectiveness (Hammayo et al., 2022). Similarly, Joseph and Onyeonu (2023) assessed public sector auditing in North Central Nigeria and established that both financial and performance audits significantly enhance accountability and transparency. Bolaji (2024) analyzed internal control mechanisms in Ibarapa East Local Government, Oyo State, and found that internal audit aids accountability by improving transparency, financial integrity, and compliance with regulations. Lanrewaju et al. (2024) explored the independence of Supreme Audit Institutions in mitigating financial fraud and concluded that weak autonomy and underfunding impair audit effectiveness. Samuel and Rufus (2024) examined transparency concerns in Nigeria's public sector and recommended judicial reforms to enhance financial accountability. Ojiya and Oga (2023) investigated the role of internal audit in financial management at a tertiary institution and found that effective auditing improves revenue generation and financial transparency. Akinteye et al. (2023) explored the role of internal audit in anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing in Nigeria, emphasizing the need for collaboration with regulatory agencies. Obafemi and Opadijo (2023) studied internal audit's impact on public teaching hospitals in Oyo State and recommended increased funding for audit departments. Ashibogwu (2023) assessed internal audit functions in Nigeria's insurance industry, revealing a positive relationship between audit committee independence and financial performance. Shodeinde et al. (2024) examined forensic accounting techniques in combating white-collar crimes and recommended the establishment of forensic audit units in public institutions. Amahi (2023) analyzed forensic accounting's role in curbing financial

crimes in the Nigerian public sector and emphasized the need for stronger internal controls. Lastly, Omimakinde and Adejuwon (2023) explored corporate governance practices and found that compliance with audit regulations significantly improves financial reporting quality.

While this research tends to study internal audit quality and performance accountability in public sector, there is paucity in research using FIRS as a case study. Also, tax administration, using performance measures like compliance with the rules of engagement, revenue collection/remission, and revenue target had not been done. However, various literature showed internal audit as tool for financial stability, some showed relationship between internal auditors and financial reporting quality and effect of Internal Auditing as a tool for accountability in private sectors and in other public sectors both within and outside Nigeria.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This present study will employ descriptive research design. Descriptive research design is considered necessary for this study because it simply describes the desired characteristics of the sample that is being studied, and the variables of study are not influenced in any way.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of 9800 staffs at the Federal Inland Revenue Service from which the target and accessible population will be drawn (FIRS, 2021).

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

Data for this study will be obtained quantitatively using random sampling techniques. Random sampling technique was used to ensure that each sample has an equal chances or probability of being chosen. Taro Yamane formula was adopted for the calculation of the sample size and the formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the required sample size, N is the total population, e is the margin of error at 95% confidence level. Therefore, the study sample size with the total population of 9800 calculated as

$$n = \frac{9800}{1 + 800(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{9800}{1 + 9800(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{9800}{1 + 24.5}$$

$$n = \frac{9800}{25.5}$$

$$n = 384.3$$

$$n = 384$$

3.4 Research Instrument

The instrument for use in the collection of the data of the study will be questionnaire named Internal Audit Quality and Public Sector Accountability in Nigeria (IAQPSA). Simple percentage and frequency count will be employed to assess the descriptive characteristics of the questionnaire-generated data. Multiple regression method was used to examine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables in order to meet the study's objectives.

4.0 Results

4.1 Instrument Response Rate

Table 1: Instrument Response Rate

S/N	Research Instruments	Amount administered	Amount retrieved	Amount Validated	Rate of Response
1	Internal Audit Quality and Public Sector Accountability in Nigeria (IAQPSA)	385	320	320	83.1%

Out of three hundred and eighty five (385) questionnaires administered to the respondents, three hundred and twenty (320) were retrieved and validated and useful for analysis, yielding a response rate of 83.1%.

4.2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents (N =320)

Demographic Variable		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	228	71.3
	Female	92	28.8
	Total	320	100
Age	Less than 30 years	15	4.7
	31-40 years	274	85.6
	41-50 years	17	5.3
	51 years and Above	14	4.4
	Total	320	100
Educational Qualification	B.Sc/HND	196	61.3
	PGD	101	31.5
	M.Sc./MBA	23	7.2
	Total	320	100
Marital Status	Single	73	22.8
	Married	236	73.8
	Divorced	11	3.4
	Total	320	100
Years of Experience	1-5 years	5	1.6
	6-10 years	14	4.4
	11-15 years	94	29.4
	16-20 years	181	56.5
	21 years and Above	26	8.1
	Total	320	100

The demographic analysis of 320 participants revealed a significant gender disparity, with males comprising 71.3% (228) and females 28.8% (92) of the sample. Age distribution showed a predominantly middle-aged workforce, with 85.6% (274) falling within the 31-40 years bracket, while other age groups represented smaller percentages. Educational qualifications indicated a well-educated respondent base, with B.Sc/HND degree holders forming the majority at 61.3% (196), followed by PGD holders at 31.5% (101), and M.Sc./MBA holders at 7.2% (23). Marital status data showed a predominantly married workforce at 73.8% (236), with single individuals at 22.8% (73) and divorced respondents at 3.4% (11). The experience profile demonstrated a highly skilled workforce, with 56.5% (181) having 16-20 years of experience, 29.4% (94) with 11-15 years, and smaller percentages in other experience brackets.

4.3 Presentation of Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the effect of effect of Internal Audit competence on compliance in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

Table 3: Internal Audit Competence on Compliance

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	M	SD	Remark
1	FIRS provides adequate resources and support to help achieve revenue targets.	41 (12.8)	270 (84.4)	9 (2.8)	0 (0)	3.10	0.38	Agree
2	The performance evaluation and rewards system at FIRS align with revenue target achievement.	45 (14.1)	259 (80.9)	16 (5)	0 (0)	3.09	0.43	Agree
3	The revenue targets set by FIRS are in line with the organization's strategic goals and objectives.	0 (0)	254 (79.4)	59 (18.4)	7 (2.2)	2.77	0.47	Agree
4	FIRS provides clear and easily accessible guidelines for	131 (40.9)	168 (52.5)	21 (6.6)	0 (0)	3.34	0.60	Agree

	taxpayers regarding payment procedures.							
5	Revenue collection at FIRS aligns with national economic goals and objectives and minimizes opportunities for tax evasion and fraud	15 (4.7)	185 (57.8)	103 (32.2)	17 (5.3)	2.61	0.66	Agree

Weighted Mean = 2.98; S.D = 0.51; Overall Decision = Agree

KEY: SA = Strongly Agree (4), A = Agree (3), D = Disagree (2) and SD = Strongly Disagree (1); S.D = Standard Deviation

*****Threshold:** mean value of 0.000-1.499 = Strongly Disagree (Very Bad); 1.500-2.499 = Disagree (Bad); 2.500-3.499 = Agree (Good); 3.500 to 4.500 = Strongly Agree (Very Good)

Table 3 shows the effect of Internal Audit competence on compliance in Federal Inland Revenue Service. From the Table, 84.4% (270) agreed that FIRS provides adequate resources and support to help achieve revenue targets, 12.8% (41) strongly agreed, 2.8% (9) of the respondents disagreed, while none of the respondents strongly disagreed. Also, the majority 80.9% (259) of the respondents agreed that revenue collection at FIRS aligns with national economic goals and objectives and minimizes opportunities for tax evasion and fraud, 14.1% (45) of the respondents strongly agreed, 5% (16) of the respondents disagreed, none strongly disagreed. Further, most of the respondents 79.4% (254) agreed that the revenue targets set by FIRS are in line with the organization's strategic goals and objectives, 18.4% (59) disagreed, 2.2% (7) of the respondents disagreed, while none of the respondents strongly agreed. Moreover, majority 52.5% (168) agreed that FIRS provides clear and easily accessible guidelines for taxpayers regarding payment procedures, 40.9% (131) strongly agreed, 6.6% (21) of the respondents disagreed while none strongly disagreed. Similarly, most 57.8% (185) of the respondent agreed that FIRS compliance process are regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changing needs and circumstances, any violations are consistently addressed, and appropriate actions are taken, 32.2% (103) of the respondents disagreed, 5.3% (17) strongly disagreed while 4.7% (15) of the respondents strongly agreed. The table generally reveals that the effect of Internal Audit competence on compliance in Federal Inland Revenue Service is good (Weighted Mean = 2.83; S.D = 0.49).

Research Question Two: What is the effect of Internal Audit control on meeting the revenue targets in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

Table 4: Internal Audit Control on Meeting the Revenue Targets

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	M	SD	Remark
1	Internal Audit plays a crucial role in controlling revenue collection processes at FIRS.	128 (40)	161 (50.3)	31 (9.7)	0 (0)	3.30	0.64	Agree (Good)
2	Internal Audit effectively identifies weaknesses and vulnerabilities in the revenue collection system	65 (20.3)	255 (79.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.20	0.40	Agree (Good)
3	The control activities of Internal Audit enhance the accuracy and reliability of revenue data.	23 (7.2)	265 (82.8)	32 (10)	0 (0)	3.01	0.57	Agree (Good)
4	Internal Audit ensures that revenue collection activities are carried out in compliance with established regulations and guidelines.	34 (10.6)	277 (86.6)	9 (2.8)	0 (0)	3.08	0.36	Agree (Good)
5	The reports and feedback provided by Internal Audit are valuable for decision-making and revenue improvement strategies	39 (12.2)	180 (56.3)	101 (31.6)	0 (0)	2.81	0.63	Agree (Good)
<p>Weighted Mean = 2.93 S.D = 0.52; Overall Decision = Agree (Good)</p>								

Table 4 shows Internal Audit Control on Meeting the Revenue Targets in Federal Inland Revenue Service. From the Table, 50.3% (161) agreed that Internal Audit plays a crucial role in controlling revenue collection processes at FIRS, 40% (128) strongly agreed, 9.7% (31) of the respondents disagreed, while none of the respondents strongly disagreed. Also, the majority of 79.7% (255) of the respondents agreed that Internal Audit effectively identifies weaknesses and vulnerabilities in the revenue collection system, 20.3% (65) strongly agreed, while none of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed. Further, most of the respondents 82.8% (265) agreed that the control activities of Internal Audit enhance the accuracy and reliability of revenue data, 7.2% (23) strongly agreed, 10% (32) of the respondents disagreed, while none strongly disagreed. Moreover, the majority 86.6% (277) agreed that Internal Audit ensures that revenue collection activities are carried out in compliance with established regulations and guidelines, 10.6% (34) strongly agreed, 2.8% (9) of the respondents disagreed while none strongly disagreed. Similarly, most 56.3% (180) of the respondents agreed that the reports and feedback provided by Internal Audit are valuable for decision-making and revenue improvement strategies, 31.6% (101) disagreed, while 12.2% (39) strongly agreed and none strongly disagreed. The table generally reveals that Internal Audit Control on Meeting the Revenue Targets in Federal Inland Revenue Service is good (Weighted Mean = 2.93; S.D = 0.52).

Research Question Three: Does Internal Audit monitoring have an impact on revenue collection in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

Table 5: Internal Audit Monitoring Impact on Revenue Collection

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	M	SD	Remark
1	Internal Audit reports its findings and recommendations without external influence or pressure	22 (6.9)	256 (84.4)	29 (9.1)	13 (4.1)	2.90	0.56	Agree (Good)
2	The monitoring of Internal Audit has a significant impact on FIRS's ability to meet its revenue targets.	186 (58.1)	103 (33.2)	7.5 (24)	7 (2.2)	3.46	0.73	Agree (Good)
3	The recommendations made by the Internal Audit department are typically followed	14.4 (46)	234 (73.1)	40 (12.5)	0 (0)	3.02	0.52	Agree (Good)

	through with and implemented effectively, leading to improved revenue collection.							
4	Internal Audit is free to conduct audits and investigations without fear of reprisal or interference	110 (34.4)	143 (44.7)	67 (20.9)	0 (0)	3.13	0.73	Agree (Good)
5	Internal Audit's independence positively contributes to the accuracy and reliability of financial data used for revenue forecasting.	38 (11.9)	159 (49.7)	123 (38.4)	0 (0)	2.73	0.66	Agree (Good)

Weighted Mean = 3.05; S.D = 0.64; Overall Decision = Agree (Good)

Table 5 shows Internal Audit Monitoring Impact on Revenue Collection in Federal Inland Revenue Service. From the Table, majority 84.4% (256) agreed that Internal Audit reports its findings and recommendations without external influence or pressure, 6.9% (22) strongly agreed, 9.1% (29) of the respondents disagreed, while 4.1% (13) strongly disagreed. Also, the majority 58.1% (186) of the respondents strongly agreed that the monitoring of Internal Audit has a significant impact on FIRS's ability to meet its revenue targets, 33.2% (103) agreed, 7.5% (24) disagreed, while 2.2% (7) strongly disagreed. Further, most of the respondents 73.1% (234) agreed that the recommendations made by the Internal Audit department are typically followed through with and implemented effectively, leading to improved revenue collection, 14.4% (46) strongly agreed, 12.5% (40) of the respondents disagreed, while none strongly disagreed. Moreover, the majority of 44.7% (143) agreed that Internal Audit is free to conduct audits and investigations without fear of reprisal or interference, 34.4% (110) strongly agreed, 20.9% (67) of the respondents disagreed while none strongly disagreed. Similarly, most 49.7% (159) of the respondents agreed that Internal Audit's independence positively contributes to the accuracy and reliability of financial data used for revenue forecasting, 38.4% (123) disagreed, while 11.9% (38) strongly agreed and none strongly disagreed. The table generally reveals that the Internal Audit Monitoring Impact on Revenue Collection in Federal Inland Revenue Service is good (Weighted Mean = 3.05; S.D = 0.64).

Research Question Four: What is the effect of Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service?

Table 6: Internal Quality on Public Sector Performance Accountability

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	M	SD	Remark
1	The internal audit function in FIRS effectively identifies and reports compliance issues.	235 (73.5)	85 (26.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4.02	0.57	Strongly Agree (Very Good)
2	Internal audit reports at FIRS are clear, accurate, and useful for improving compliance with the rules of engagement	224 (69.9)	81 (25.3)	12 (3.6)	3.8 (1.2)	3.89	0.50	Strongly Agree (Very Good)
3	The internal audit department at FIRS conducts regular and thorough assessments of compliance with rules and regulations	228 (71.1)	92 (28.9)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.95	0.45	Strongly Agree (Very Good)
4	The internal audit department at FIRS provides valuable insights and recommendations for continuous improvement in compliance efforts	191 (59.8)	129 (40.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.90	0.50	Strongly Agree (Very Good)
5	All audits are carried out with confidentiality and established code of conduct	15 (4.7)	185 (57.8)	103 (32.2)	17 (5.3)	2.61	0.66	Agree (Good)

Weighted Mean = 3.67; S.D = 0.54; Overall Decision = Strongly Agree (Very Good)

Table 6 evaluates the Internal Quality of Public Sector Performance Accountability at the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The results show that the internal audit function at FIRS is highly regarded for its effectiveness in ensuring compliance. A majority of respondents, 73.5% (235), strongly agreed that the internal audit function effectively identifies and reports compliance issues, with a weighted mean of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.57, indicating "Very Good" performance. Similarly, 69.9% (224) strongly agreed that internal audit reports are clear, accurate, and useful for improving compliance, yielding a mean of 3.89 and an SD of 0.50. Furthermore, a majority of 71.1% (228) strongly agreed that the internal audit department conducts thorough assessments of compliance, with a mean of 3.95 and an SD of 0.45, and 59.8% (191) strongly agreed that valuable insights and recommendations are provided for continuous improvement, scoring 3.90 and an SD of 0.50. However, when assessing confidentiality and adherence to the code of conduct during audits, only 4.7% (15) strongly agreed, and 57.8% (185) agreed, resulting in a lower mean of 2.61 and an SD of 0.66, categorized as "Good." Overall, the internal audit's impact on accountability at FIRS is considered "Very Good," with a weighted mean of 3.67 and an SD of 0.54.

4.4 Presentation of Hypotheses

H₀₁: To what extent does combined influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service

Table 7: ANOVA for the Combined Influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit Quality on Public Sector Performance Accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.391	2	1.195	14.575	.000 ^b
	Residual	73.509	317	1.987		
	Total	75.900	319			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance Accountability in FIRS

b. Predictors: (Constant), Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit Quality

Fvalue is significant at P<0.05

Table 8: Model Summary of Combined Influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit Quality on Public Sector Performance Accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.448 ^a	.701	.620	.30817

a. b. Predictors: (Constant), Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit Quality

Table 7 and 8 shows the model summary and ANOVA of multiple regression analysis for the combined influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. The table shows that the F- value is 14.575 and the p-value is .000 (F= 14.575, P<0.05) which is much less than 0.05 and highly significant since p-value (.000 < 0.05) at 95% confidence level. The F-test rejects the null hypothesis that states none of the independent variables have a significant relationship with public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service and it can be concluded that there exists variation in Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service and the relationship is significant which means that the regression model is a good fit of the data. This suggests that Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality significantly influence public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. The model summary on Table 4.11 shows the R² value of 0.71 which implies that 71% variation in public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. (dependent variable) could be explained by the independent variables (combined influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality). The remaining 29% is explained by other factors outside the model and the error term. An R² value greater than 0.5 means that the model is effective enough to determine the relationship. In this case, the value is 0.62, which is also good. The adjusted R² value shows that 62% of the variance in public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service is explained only by the independent variables which are to be kept in the model. This therefore

means that the remaining 38% could be a result of other predictors included or added to the model that do not have a significant prediction on academic achievement in literacy of preschool children. Furthermore, the very little difference between the R^2 value and Adjusted R^2 value (that is, $0.71 - .62 = .09$) indicates a very good fit of the model because the closer the R^2 value is to the adjusted R^2 , the better the fit of the model.

H02: There will be no significant relative influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service.

Table 9: Coefficients of Multiple Regression Analysis of Relative Influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit Quality on Public Sector Performance Accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.571	.331		7.098	.000
	Internal competence	Audit .112	.047	.147	2.357	.019
	Internal control	Audit .121	.113	.202	1.064	.008
	Internal monitoring	Audit .150	.052	.302	3.120	.000
	Internal Quality	Audit .101	.100	.198	1.768	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Public Sector Performance Accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service

Table 9 shows the coefficients of multiple regression analysis for the relative influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. These results of the table implies that Internal Audit competence (Beta = .147; t = 2.357; Significance = .019), Internal

Audit control (Beta = .202; $t = 1.064$; Significance = .008), Internal Audit monitoring (Beta = .302; $t = 3.120$; Significance = .000), Internal Audit Quality (Beta = .198; $t = 1.786$; Significance = .000) which are significant at $P > 0.05$ structure explained the variance in in Federal Inland Revenue Service and therefore needed in the model. Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality have a positive relationship with public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service as depicted by their positive B value of .112, .121, .150 and .101 respectively. This result implies that as it increases, the dependent variable also increases. It therefore means that Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality influenced Public Sector Performance Accountability in this study. For a unit change in Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality .112, .121, .150 and .101 respectively there is an increase in Public Sector Performance Accountability as depicted by the positive value of B. Similarly, the computed empirical value of F-test is 14.575 which is significant at $p = 0.00$. It is therefore concluded that the F-test is statistically significant. The independents variables (Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality) statistically and significantly predict the dependent variable (Public Sector Performance Accountability). This therefore accomplished part of the research aim “To establish the influence of Internal Audit on public sector performance accountability. Hence, the null hypothesis should be rejected because the test is statistically significant. Therefore, the whole regression is statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

Results of the demographic data analysis of the respondents showed that 71.3% (228) of the respondents are male, while 28.8% (92) of the respondents are female. This shows that, majority of the FIRS staff in Oyo State are Male. The results also showed that those that fall within the age range of 31 and 40 years are more in this study, 4.7% (15) were less than 30 years, 5.3% (17) of the respondents were within the age range of 41 and 50 years, while 4.4% of the respondents were 51 years and above. Also, majority 73.8% (236) of the respondents are married, 22.8% (73) of the respondents are single and 3.4% (11) of the respondents are separated. This suggests that a major portion of the respondents in FIRS Oyo state are married. Findings of the study showed degree holders 61.3% (196) (BSc./HND) are more in the study, which is an indication that majority of FIRS staff are either university or polytechnic graduates. 31.5% (101) of the respondents have PGDE, while 7.2% (23) holds MSc./MBA certificate. These collaborates the findings of Oussii & Boulila Taktak (2018) which reported 202 (57.7 percent) of the respondents are male, while 148 (42.3 percent) are female. The majority, 182 (52 percent) are married, 148 (42.3 percent) are single, while 20 (5.7 percent) are divorced. Further, majority of the respondents, 56.6% (185) of the respondents have working experience between 15-20 years, 41.6% (5) of the respondents have working experience between 1-5 years, 4.4% (14) of the respondents have 6-10 years working experience, 29.4% (94) of the respondents have experience between 11-15 years while 8.1 (26) of the respondents have working experience for over 20 years. This clearly indicates that most of the

FIRS staff are well experienced. This result opposes a finding of Pizzini et al. (2015) which revealed that the majority of 47% of the respondents were employed 5-10 years, 41% were employed in less than 5 years, 11-15 years has 10% while 16 and above years has 2%.

Finding from research question one, internal audit competence has a good overall effect on compliance at FIRS, with a weighted mean of 2.83 and a standard deviation of 0.49 (Weighted Mean = 2.83; S.D = 0.49). The positive mean score underscores the effectiveness of the internal audit functions in maintaining compliance standards within FIRS. The findings suggest that FIRS is largely successful in providing the necessary resources and support to its staff, aligning its operations with national economic goals, and providing clear guidelines to taxpayers. However, there are areas of concern regarding the alignment of revenue targets with strategic objectives and the adaptability of compliance processes. Kenayathulla et al. (2019) reported that the competence of internal auditors significantly influenced internal audit effectiveness within Nigeria's Federal Public Service, which manages a substantial portion of the nation's public revenues. Urquia (2018) emphasized the importance of internal audit competence, showing that it had a positive and significant contribution to internal audit's ability to meet its objectives.

Findings from research question three showed there is a good overall perception of Internal Audit's control in meeting the revenue targets at FIRS, with a weighted mean of 2.93 and a standard deviation of 0.52 (Weighted Mean = 2.93; S.D = 0.52). These findings suggest that while there is strong appreciation for the functional aspects of Internal Audit, there may be areas for improvement in enhancing its impact on strategic decision-making and revenue optimization. This result is in line with the findings of Mafundu & Mafini (2019) that demonstrated that tax audits significantly influence various types of tax revenues including petroleum profit tax, company income tax, and value-added tax. The research underscores the effectiveness of tax audits in enhancing revenue generation for the Federal Inland Revenue Service of Nigeria. Christopher et al. (2009) highlighted that forensic audit services play a significant role in mitigating tax fraud, thereby improving tax revenue generation in Nigeria. This study suggests the importance of audit quality in achieving revenue targets.

Findings from research question three suggests that the impact of Internal Audit monitoring on revenue collection in FIRS is generally viewed positively, with a weighted mean of 3.05 and a standard deviation of 0.52 (Weighted Mean = 3.05; S.D = 0.52). This findings is in line with a study by Abiodun (2020) examined tax administration and its impact on tax revenue generation, highlighting the role of tax audit mechanisms as essential for monitoring tax collection effectively, thus supporting improved revenue outcomes. Calvin (2020) also emphasises that strengthened audit departments can enhance revenue collection. Roussy et al. (2020) suggests that integrating robust auditing practices can improve revenue generation, although it notes that forensic accounting was not a major contributing factor during the study period. It recommends enhancing forensic auditing capabilities to boost revenue collection efforts.

Findings from research question four illustrates a high level of satisfaction with the internal audit's role in enhancing public sector performance accountability, as indicated by an overall weighted mean of 3.67 (Weighted Mean = 3.67; S.D = 0.54) which is very good. Kenayathulla et al. (2015) which reported that auditor competence significantly enhances audit effectiveness, thereby supporting accountability in public sector organizations, including FIRS. Bento et al. (2018) highlighted the positive relationship between the quality of internal audit functions and public sector performance, demonstrating the internal audit's crucial role in enhancing accountability and performance in the public sector, including entities like FIRS.

Further, findings from hypothesis one showed that there is a significant combined influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. The F-test rejects the null hypothesis that states none of the independent variables have a significant relationship with public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service ($F=14.575$, $P<0.05$) and it can be concluded that there exists variation in Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service and the relationship is significant which means that the regression model is a good fit of the data. Botha & Wilkinson (2020) found that robust internal controls significantly enhance the quality of financial reporting, indicating that similar effects can be expected in public sector settings like the FIRS.

Findings from hypothesis two also showed that there is a significant relative influence of Internal Audit competence, Internal Audit control, Internal Audit monitoring and Internal Audit quality on public sector performance accountability in Federal Inland Revenue Service. Internal Audit competence (Beta = .147; $t = 2.357$; Significance = .019), Internal Audit control (Beta = .202; $t = 1.064$; Significance = .008), Internal Audit monitoring (Beta = .302; $t = 3.120$; Significance = .000), Internal Audit Quality (Beta = .198; $t = 1.786$; Significance = .000) which are significant at $P>0.05$ explained the variance in in Federal Inland Revenue Service. Chapman (2019) explored how internal audit quality impacts public sector management in Nigeria, showing that internal audit competence, objectivity, challenges, and performance positively relate to effective public sector management and partly corroborates these findings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the influence of internal audit on public sector performance accountability within the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that internal audit competence, control, monitoring, and quality significantly contribute to enhancing accountability and revenue collection.

The independence of the audit process ensures reliable findings, which play a crucial role in strategic decision-making. However, concerns about confidentiality and adherence to the code of conduct during audits suggest areas for potential improvement. Statistical analyses further confirmed the strong impact of internal audit functions on governance, compliance, and overall organizational performance at FIRS. FIRS should ensure that internal audit activities are closely aligned with its strategic goals by regularly reviewing and updating the audit framework to reflect changes in priorities and regulations.

The organization should invest in continuous professional training and development for audit staff, particularly in areas such as forensic auditing and cybersecurity, to enhance their effectiveness. It is essential to safeguard the independence of the internal audit function by implementing policies that protect auditors from external influence and internal pressure.

Additionally, FIRS should establish a more effective system for tracking audit recommendations, ensuring that findings are properly implemented and integrated into decision-making processes for better governance and accountability.

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